

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANT OF ALKALINE EARTH METAL-CPTA COMPLEXES

 $\mu = 0.19 M$, temp = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Metal(II)	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
Be	6.46 (± 0.03)	4.90 (± 0.05)
Mg	6.00 (± 0.05)	—
Ca	6.15 (± 0.04)	2.90 (± 0.06)
Sr	5.90 (± 0.05)	2.85 (± 0.04)
Ba	5.38 (± 0.07)	2.84 (± 0.04)

TABLE 2—INFRARED ABSORPTION PEAKS OF CARBOXYLIC GROUPS (ANTISYM. AND SYM.) AND THEIR DIFFERENCES IN ALKALINE EARTH METAL COMPLEXES

Metal(II)	ν_{COO^-} (antisym.) cm^{-1}	ν_{COO^-} (sym.) cm^{-1}	Frequency difference cm^{-1}
Be	1 600	1 379	221
Mg	1 550	1 360	190
Ca	1 540	1 388	152
Sr	1 540	1 418	122
Ba	1 526	1 408	118

mmetrical and symmetrical vibrations and their differences in CPTA-alkaline earth metal complexes. It can be seen that the differences of the frequencies in the region 1 660 to 1 525 and 1 420 to 1 360 cm^{-1} show the decrease in the order, $Be^{2+} > Mg^{2+} > Ca^{2+} > Sr^{2+} > Ba^{2+}$ which is also the order of their ionic radii. This suggests that the order of decreasing stabilities of the complexes should also be same¹¹. This is true for stability values except there is reversal in case of Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} complexes because Mg^{2+} forms hydrate bonds in aqueous medium.

The study indicates that Be—O bond is less ionic in character than other alkaline earth metal complexes and this trend increases with the increase in their ionic radii.

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Effect of Nitro Group on the Mass Spectra of Quinazolinone Derivatives[†]

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BEHAVIOUR of 4(3H-quinazolinone derivatives under electron impact have been studied earlier¹⁻³ but no attempt, however, appears to have been made to study the effect of nitro group on the phenyl part of the quinazolinone ring. In the absence of appropriate deuterated compounds, an attempt has been made to study the gross change in the breakdown pattern under electron impact ionisation conditions in the mass spectral study of this class of compounds possessing substituents on the phenyl part of the quinazolinone ring. The results obtained with the EI-MS-computer system are presented in this communication.

(6) R = CH₃, R₁ = morpholino

Earlier studies of various quinazolinone derivatives studied under electron impact mass spectrometry invariably led to the fragmentation of the pyrimidine part of the quinazolinone ring. Substituents such as nitro group with or without *ortho*-amino function should, in principle, exhibit their well known behaviour under electron impact⁴. Studies carried out with 1-6 revealed that the heterocyclic ring in 1 was not cleaved initially. The percentage abundance of the peaks appearing due to the loss of O, NO, NO₂ and also due to the loss of CO, CH₃CN and (CO + HCN) fragments, suggest that the predominant pathway of the breakdown appears to be mediated through the NO₂ group. In compounds 2-5, the absence of peaks

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(1)

(5)

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for M^+CO , M^+CH_3CN and M^+HCN clearly indicated that the breakdown did not initiate from the pyrimidine part of the quinazolone ring. The presence of peaks for M^+H , M^+CH_3 , M^+O , M^+H-O , M^+NO , M^+NO_2 and M^+H-NO_2 in these compounds clearly revealed that the substituents at positions 6 and 7 participated in the breakdown of these compounds. Compound 6 disappeared immediately under the conditions used for compounds 2-5, in the mass spectrometer and so had to be recorded at lower probe temperature. The observed peaks, however, supported the aforementioned behaviour reported for 2-5. Computer print out of 1, 5 and 6 along with their percentage abundance is presented for the sake of clarity. The preparation of the compounds studied have been reported earlier⁵.

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¹³C Nmr Study of 5-Aryl-4-(3-methyl-5-styryl-4-isoxazolyl)-3-phenyl- Δ^2 -1,2,4-oxadiazolines

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THE synthesis and mass spectral behaviour¹ of 5-aryl-4-(3-methyl-5-styryl-4-isoxazolyl)-3-phenyl- Δ^2 -1,2,4-oxadiazolines have been reported from these laboratories. ¹³C nmr spectra of these compounds is discussed in this paper and this happens to be the first ever report on ¹³C nmr data of isoxazolyloxadiazolines. ¹³C nmr study of isoxazoloazepines has earlier been reported by us².

The chemical shift values of the various carbons of five isoxazolyloxadiazolines (1-5) studied, have been presented in Table 1. The assignments are based on chemical shifts, off-resonance multiplicities and internal consistency. In the spectrum of 3,5-diphenyl-4-isoxazolyloxadiazoline (1) with wide-band proton decoupling sixteen lines have been